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Unilateral accessory lobe and unusual isthmus of thyroid gland: a cadaver study

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Abstract

Background: The thyroid gland is known to exhibit various congenital malformations with regard to its lobes, isthmus and ectopic sites. Knowledge of variations in topographical anatomy of thyroid gland is essential for safe surgery and logical interpretation of scintigraphs.

Objective: To study the anomalous isthmus and accessory lobe of the thyroid gland.

Materials and methods: The thyroid gland was studied for presence of any accessory lobe and abnormal isthmus in 40 cadavers over a period of five years.

Results: We observed a single case of accessory lobe of thyroid gland with unusual isthmus.

Conclusion: Although an accessory lobe of thyroid gland may not manifest clinically, its clinical and academic importance cannot be undermined. Presence of such anomalies may also be important for clinicians, radiologists and other medical professionals in day to day clinical practice.

Key Words: Thyroid, accessory, isthmus, anatomy, variation, anomaly.

Introduction

Normally, the thyroid gland consists of two lobes connected by an isthmus. The isthmus connects the lower parts of the two lobes of the gland and measures 1.25 cm in its vertical and horizontal dimension respectively [1].

Conventional textbooks of anatomy describe the isthmus to be located anterior to the second and third tracheal cartilage but it may be found displaced above or below its usual level [1]. Interestingly, the isthmus in the present case, did not display the usual dimensions. Thereby suggesting it to be a congenital anomaly.

Many congenital malformations of the thyroid gland involving the lateral lobes, isthmus, pyramidal lobes, aplasia or

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hemiagenesis, ectopic sites of the gland have been reported [2, 3, 4, 5]. The accessory lobe of the thyroid gland has been reported to be situated at various regions and has been thought to be apparently developing from a compartmentalized portion of the primordial of the right lobe and forming a separate lobe [4].

Material and Method

The thyroid gland was carefully examined in forty dissected cadavers over a period of five years. An anomalous thyroid gland was detected in a 48 year male cadaver during traditional undergraduate teaching program. The observations pertaining to the morphological features of the gland were recorded and an appropriate photograph was taken.

Results

An anomalous thyroid gland on the left side, the accessory lobe was separated by a thin septum from the main gland

An unusual isthmus whose vertical dimension was more than the transverse and a small unilateral accessory lobe of the gland could be referred to as a congenital anomaly. A thorough insight into normal and abnormal anatomy of thyroid gland may be important for surgical, radiological and clinical purposes.

Figure. (1) shows a small accessory lobe of the gland located on the superior aspect of the thyroid gland on the left side.

Figure (1): Dissected specimen of thyroid gland: (1) Right lobe, (2) Left lobe, (3) Isthmus, (4) Trachea, (5) Thyroid cartilage, (6) Accessory part of the gland is shown with small arrow (↑)

This accessory lobe (marked with an arrow) could be delineated from the main gland by a thin septum. The isthmus was located in front of the third and fourth tracheal cartilages. It measured 2.2 cm and 1.1 cm in its vertical and transverse dimensions respectively. The lobes of the thyroid gland displayed a tapering apex. The lobes of thyroid gland measured 2.5 and 2.2 cm as its maximum transverse dimension on the left and right sides respectively. The gland was as usual supplied by the superior and the inferior thyroid arteries. No accessory lobe was detected on the right side.

Discussion

The thyroid gland is known to develop from the epithelial proliferation in the floor of the pharynx between the tuberculum impar and the copula [6]. Thereby, the thyroid gland descends anterior to the pharyngeal gut, as a bilobed diverticulum and remains connected to the tongue by the thyroglossal duct, which disappears later [6]. In the due course of embryonic development, the gland descends in front of the hyoid bone and by seven weeks, it reaches the final position in front of the trachea, to have two lobes and a connecting isthmus [6]. Morphological variations of the thyroid gland are generally found in the superior part of the gland [4]. Further in the present case, we observed a gland with the maximum transverse dimension of the left side lobe being greater than that of the right lobe. The greater transverse dimension of the left lobe of thyroid gland is an evidence of asymmetry in the profile of the gland, an observation which is consistent with an earlier report [7]. Malformations of the thyroid gland. Many of the past research have reported the common congenital anomalies to be aplasia or hemigenesis of the gland [2, 8]. There are few reports on the anomalies of the isthmus of the thyroid gland or its peculiar dimensions although there have been reports on the absence of the isthmus of the thyroid gland [9]. The present case was unique since it described unusual dimensions of the isthmus i.e. its vertical dimension being more than that of the width. The accessory thyroid gland is apparently thought to be developing from a compartmentalized portion of the primordium of the right lobe, thereby

forming a separate lobe [4]. Research workers have stated that small portions of the thyroid primordium separate from the diverticulum and may become associated with developing heart and septum transversarium [4]. Thus there are possibilities of finding thyroid tissue at different places i.e. even near the heart and the diaphragm [4]. Although every anomaly of the thyroid gland may not manifest with symptoms, awareness of its existence is important to surgeons. Admittedly, in the present case, the clinical history of the individual was not available to corroborate observations. Undoubtedly, prior knowledge about anatomical variations of the thyroid gland is important from academic as well as clinical viewpoint.

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